

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Farmers' assessment of soil quality in Galicia (Atlantic Spain)

Healthy soil is crucial for food production, yet over 60% of EU soils are in poor condition due to farming, pollution, and climate change. The SoildiverAgro project seeks to understand farmers' decisions on sustainable soil management and promote practices that improve soil health, boost crop yields, and benefit the environment. Farmers who believe in sustainable soil practices are more likely to try them, especially if they see support from their community, neighbors, and agricultural groups. Success stories, expert advice, and financial help can give them the confidence to make lasting changes. But overall, it is important to understand how farmers define good soil, how they assess it, and how much they believe their actions can help solve soil problems.

In Galicia, the Atlantic region of Spain, the study focused on crop diversification—growing different species (e.g., potatoes

and vegetables) either together or in rotation—to enhance soil quality. It gathered data from 62 completed questionnaires, with consent, through collaboration with research centers, farmers' associations, local groups, agricultural newspapers, and social media accounts of participating organizations.

As in other regions, Galician farmers rated their soil as either “rather good” (48%) or “neither good nor bad” (47%). The most common indicators for evaluating soil quality included pH levels (63%), crop yield (60%), organic matter content (53%), and soil structure (52%). Farmers in this region particularly focused on soil moisture and structure when considering improvements.

1. Wheat field assay carried out in the SoildiverAgro project.

KEYWORDS

Soil health, sustainable management, crop diversification, farmer perception, soil degradation

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